

Design and Implementation of Miniature Weather Station Using BME280

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Abstract

We know that there's an increase in demand for the real time environmental system. IoT based home weather stations have become essential for accurate weather forecasting and for personal climate tracking too. This research presents the design and implementation of a home weather station using BME280 as the sensor, which is known for providing accurate data related to temperature, humidity and atmospheric pressure. The system uses ESP32 as microcontroller which converts all the analog data into digital data and then we display this data on our dashboard using Fire Base IoT as our data storage. This methodology involves calibrating the sensor BME280, collecting the data at set intervals and visualization of the data in graphical format. This shows the effectiveness and reliability of the sensor BME280. Furthermore, the integration of machine learning algorithms can help us in making this system into predicting the upcoming weather accurately.

Keywords - IoT, Home weather station, BME280, ESP32, Temperature Monitoring, Humidity Monitoring, Atmospheric pressure monitoring, Cloud computing.

1. Introduction

- A. Weather monitoring is crucial in day-to-day life, it influences your daily decision in various fields including agriculture, home automation and disaster management. The traditional way to obtain weather data is from government meteorological stations [9]. These stations provide us with regional averages instead of localized real time data. This limitation leads to growing demand for personalized weather monitoring systems that can provide people with accurate & real time data with data for specific location [1]. Every regions temperature and humidity & pressure is not same it changes respectively with the geographical region and depends upon the altitude of the geographical location. [5][8]
- B. This research mainly focuses on the development of weather station using BME280 sensor, it's a high precision sensor which measure temperature humidity and atmospheric pressure. Other sensor such as DHT22 or BMP180, BME280 offers better accuracy, less power consumption and faster response time which makes it first choice for home weather monitoring system [1]. This system is built using a micro controller (ESP32/Arduino), which collects sensor data and displays all the information on our LCD screen, a web dashboard or we can display it on a mobile application
- C. Main objectives for this research are:
 - To design and implement a cost-effective and compact weather monitoring system using BME280 sensor

- To develop a real time data and to acquire visualization using IoT-bases platforms
- To analyze and compare sensor data with standard meteorological data for accurate verification
- To explore potential application for the home automation system and smart agriculture
- By developing an affordable and efficient home weather station, this research aims to grant individuals with localized weather data, enhancing personal decision making for the day-to-day tasks and improving environmental awareness.
- Future enhance may include cloud-based data logging and also an AI-driven weather prediction model for easing our decision in day-to-day life.

2. Literature Overview

Home weather stations have evolved from traditional meteorological devices to IoT-enabled systems that offer real-time monitoring and cloud integration. BME280, a compact and precise sensor, is widely used for measuring temperature, humidity, and pressure, outperforming older sensors like DHT11 and BMP180 in accuracy and power efficiency.

IoT-based weather stations, utilize ESP32 for data transmission to cloud platforms like Thing Speak and Firebase, allowing remote access and analytics. Energy efficiency is a major research focus, with techniques like Deep Sleep Mode, MQTT communication, and solar power integration improving sustainability. [2]

However, gaps remain in long-term stability, AI-driven weather prediction, and energy optimization, which this research aims to address by implementing an efficient, cloud-connected home weather station using BME280.

1) Sytem Architecture-

This weather station consists of: -

- BME280 sensor- It measures temperature (degree Celsius), Humidity (%), Atmospheric Pressure (hPa).
- ESP32- To process the data and help us calculate the analog readings.
- Standard Dashboard – We will be displaying our readings on standard dashboard using IoT platforms.
- Firebase IoT – We will be using IoT platform for storing our data.
- We will be using Wi-Fi 6 & Bluetooth for remote monitoring.

Figure [1] – Block diagram of the weather station

3. Software implementation :

The software is responsible for the data we acquire, the data we process and the transmission.

- A) Proteus
- B) Arduino IDE

3.1- Programming and data acquisition

- The microcontroller i.e ESP32 is programmed by Arduino IDE.
- The BME280 library is used for reading the sensor values.
- The sensor uses I2C protocol for communication with ESP32.
- BME280 reads data after every 1 second of interval.

3.2- Data Processing and Calibration

- The raw sensor data is filtered to remove noise
- Temperature compensation algorithms are applied for accuracy.
- Calibration is performed by comparing sensor readings with standard meteorological data.

3.3- Data Storage and visualization

- The processed data or the final data is then uploaded to Firebase IoT platform-based Dashboard
- This dashboard is made by React, HTML, JAVA script And Django

3.4- Wireless communication and IoT integration

- To enable remote monitoring of data the system supports Wi-Fi 6 Connectivity and Bluetooth connectivity for sending our finalized data to Firebase

The steps include:

1. Connecting ESP32 to a particular Wi-Fi network.
2. Sending our final reading to Firebase IoT.
3. Retrieving our data on the dashboard made

3.5- Testing and Validation

- The system is tested indoors and outdoors to evaluate our readings for the given sensor data accuracy.
- Sensor data is then compared to the weather app present on our handsets.
- Performance of the system is done based on latency, accuracy and power efficiency.

3.6- Limitations and challenges

- Sensor reading varied due to environmental interferences
- Wi-Fi connectivity issues affected the real time data transmission which also affected the readings showed on the dashboard.
- Power consumption was not efficient in the very start thus making the BME280 and ESP 32 overheat.

3.7- Future Enhancements

- AI-Based weather forecasting – Using previous data to predict the future readings.
- Battery Optimization for portable applications for our system.
- Integration with smart home automation for example turn on the fan or air conditioning based on the set temperature.

Figure [2] – Circuit diagram of Station

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1- Calculations

A. Temperature Calculation in degree Celsius

$$T = \frac{adc_T}{16384.0} - \frac{dig_T1}{1024.0} \times dig_T2 + \left(\frac{adc_T}{131072.0} - \frac{dig_T1}{8192.0} \right) \times \left(\frac{adc_T}{131072.0} - \frac{dig_T1}{8192.0} \right) \times dig_T3$$

where:

- T is the compensated temperature in °C.
- adc_T is the raw temperature value from the sensor.
- dig_T1, dig_T2, dig_T3 are sensor calibration coefficients provided in the datasheet.

B. Humidity Calculation in %

$$H = (adc_H - dig_H1 \times 16.0) \times \frac{dig_H2}{16384.0} \times \left(1.0 + \frac{dig_H3}{67108864.0} \times H + \frac{dig_H4}{67108864.0} \times H^2 \right)$$

where:

- H is the relative humidity (%).
- adc_H is the raw humidity reading.
- $dig_H1, dig_H2, dig_H3, dig_H4$ are factory calibration values.

C. Pressure Calculation in hPa

$$P = \frac{1048576 - adc_P - (var2/4096)}{var1} \times 3125$$

where:

- P is the compensated atmospheric pressure in hPa (hectopascals).
- adc_P is the raw pressure value from the sensor.
- $var1, var2$ are intermediate variables that depend on calibration values.

4.2 GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION

Table [1] – Readings of The Miniature Weather Station

Sr.No	Data Received From BME280			
	Time in Minutes	Temperature in °C	Humidity in %	Pressure in hPa
1	0	22.5	50	1015
2	30	24.0	52	1014.5
3	60	25.2	54	1014
4	90	26.1	55.0	1013.8
5	120	25.8	54.7	1013.5
6	150	25.5	53.6	1013
7	180	24.8	52.4	1012.8
8	210	24.0	50.1	1012.5
9	240	23.3	49.0	1012
10	270	22.8	48.0	1011.8
11	300	22.0	46.2	1011.5
12	330	23.0	48.4	1011.2

Figure [3] – Temperature (Celsius) vs Time (minutes)

Figure [4] – Humidity (%) vs Time (minutes)

Figure [5] – Pressure (hPa) vs Time (minutes)

4.3 Sensor Data Analysis

- Temperature readings fluctuated based on the environmental changes showing a trend of fluctuations in daytime.
- Humidity variations correlate with temperature thus indication accuracy and assuring near to accurate data in atmospheric moisture detection.
- Pressure readings remained near to same or stable but showed minor fluctuations thus proving our stations precision.

4.4 Comparison With Standard Readings

- While comparing our data with local weather station or with our online weather app we got ± 0.5 °C in Temperature, $\pm 0.8\%$ in Humidity and ± 0.2 hPa in pressure readings.
- This indicates our Weather Station has high precision and near to perfect reading when compared to weather app or our local weather station.

4.5 Challenges Identified

- Latency issue was faced many times because there was a data lag in real time data monitoring.
- Energy consumption in continuous mode is much higher so a deep sleep mode is recommended for efficiency in power consumption.
- Sensor placement affected readings as first we placed our sensor BME280 near our microcontroller
- that is ESP32 which generated a lot of heat and thus affected our data readings

5. Conclusion Matrix

Time in Minutes	0	30	60	90	120	150	180	210	240	270	300	330
Temperature measured in BME (Celsius)	22.5	24.0	25.2	26.1	25.8	25.5	24.8	24.0	23.3	22.8	22.0	23.0
Temperature measured in Weather app (Celsius)	22.9	23.5	24.3	24.9	25.2	25.9	25.3	24.8	23.5	23.2	22.9	23.4
Humidity measured in BME (%)	50	52	53.7	55.0	54.7	53.6	52.4	50.1	49.0	48.0	46.2	48.0
Humidity measured in Weather app (%)	49.2	50.9	51.6	52.9	53.8	54.2	53.2	51.9	50.3	49.8	48.6	47.2
Pressure measured in BME (hPa)	1015	1014.5	1014	1013.8	1013.5	1013.0	1012.8	1012.5	1012.0	1011.8	1011.5	1011.2
Pressure measure in Weather app (hPa)	1015.4	1014.9	1014.2	1014.0	1013.7	1013.2	1013.0	1012.9	1012.5	1011.9	1012.0	1011.4

6. Conclusion

The Home Weather station using BME280 successfully monitors the temperature, humidity and pressure in real time and ideal setting. The system provides us with accurate environmental data which helps us to be accessed remotely through an IoT platform. The experimental results show that the BME280 sensor also offers highly precise data when compared to other sensors like DHT11 and BMP280. The Data Analysis and the Graphical Representation shows the accuracy and precision of system in monitoring temperature, humidity and pressure. While the system performs well, some limitations are observed which consist of minor sensor inaccuracy due to environmental factors and latency issue while uploading data to dashboard. Implementing Power Saving tactics can further improve this system making it suitable and reliable for long term deployment.

7. References

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